

■ Island ■ N_Shore ■ S_Shore
 ■ N_Shelf ■ S_Shelf □ Open Sea

A) Dietary folate: DMR.F1

B) Dietary folate: DMR.F2

C) Alcohol intake: DMR.A1

D) Alcohol intake: DMR.A2